

These data clearly indicate structure (II) assigned for these compounds formed by the usual Stobbe mechanism⁶.

(Ar = phenyl, *p*-methoxyphenyl, 3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl, 3 : 4-dimethoxyphenyl and furyl).

Experimental

Condensation of anisylidene acetophenone with dimethyl succinate :

Anisylidene acetophenone⁷ (5 g.) and dimethyl succinate (3.5 g) were added to a solution of potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol (from 1 g. potassium in 30 ml. *t*-butanol), and mechanically stirred under inert anhydrous conditions for 45 min. The reaction mixture was acidified to congo-red with 6 *N* hydrochloric acid and the *t*-butanol was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was repeatedly extracted with ether and ether phase was extracted with ice-cold sodium carbonate solution. The alkaline layer was acidified and the resulting sticky solid was taken up in ether. Removal of solvent gave an orange material, (3.7 g.). Crystallization from solvents yielded sticky and clumped solid material, but chromatographic purification on silica-gel with petroleum ether-benzene eluant gave the crystalline solid, 3-carbomethoxy-4-phenyl-6-*p*-methoxyphenyl-hex-3,5-dienoic acid (II, Ar = *p*-methoxyphenyl), m.p. 70°-71°. Found : Eq. wt. 352, C, 71.6; H, 5.41, reqd. for C₂₁H₂₀O₆ : eq. wt. 352, C, 71.8; H, 5.45%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) = 228 (4.04), 246 (4.00), 334 (4.11). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1689, 1717 and 1734 cm⁻¹.

Similarly piperonylidene acetophenone gave (II, Ar = 3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl), m.p. 80°-81°. (Found : eq. wt. 366, C, 69.33; H, 4.68, reqd. for C₂₁H₁₈O₆ : eq. wt. 366, C, 69.04; H, 4.66%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) 244 (3.99), 290 (3.83) and 348 (3.95). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1689, 1717 and 1738 cm⁻¹. Veratralidene acetophenone gave (II, Ar = 3 : 4-dimethoxyphenyl), m.p. 69°-70°. Found : eq. wt. 383, C, 69.4; H, 5.47, reqd. for C₂₂H₂₂O₆ : eq. wt. 382, C, 69.1; H, 5.75%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) 230 (4.39), 336 (4.29). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1689, 1717 and 1730 cm⁻¹. Benzylidene acetophenone gave (II, Ar = phenyl), m.p. 72°-73°. Found : eq.wt.

324, C, 74.7; H, 5.62, reqd. for C₂₀H₁₈O₄ : Eq. wt. 322, C, 74.52; H, 5.59%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) 240 (4.15), 315 (4.27). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1695, 1710 and 1730 cm⁻¹. Furfurylidene acetophenone gave (II, Ar = furyl), m.p. 78°-79°. Found : eq. wt. 311, C, 69.6; H, 5.14, reqd. for C₁₈H₁₆O₅ : eq. wt. 312, C, 69.23; H, 5.12%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) 248 (3.95), 365 (3.96). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1685, 1717 and 1725 cm⁻¹.

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References

1. a) H. STOBBE and L. RUSSWURM, *Ann.*, 1901, **314**, 125.
b) H. STOBBE, *Ann.*, 1901, **314**, 111.
2. a) W. S. JOHNSON and G. H. DAUB, *Org. Reactions*, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1951, Vol. 6, p. 11, 68.
b) K. R. RAO and G. BAGAVANT, *Current Sci.*, 1969, **38**, 11.
3. A. I. SCOTT, *Interpretation of Ultraviolet Spectra of Natural Products*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1964, p. 109.
4. L. J. BELLAMY, *The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules*, Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1958, p. 65.
5. *Idem.*, *Ibid.*, p. 34.
6. W. S. JOHNSON, A. L. MCCLOSKEY and D. A. DUNNINGAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 514.
7. H. GILMAN and A. H. BLATT (Ed.), *Organic Synthesis*, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, *Coll. Vol. 1*, 1951, p. 79.

Complex Compounds of Diphenyl Lead-dichloride with Multidentate Schiff Bases

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IN continuation of our research programme on non-transitional metal complexes of nitrogen-containing ligands¹, the investigation on the reaction of diphenyllead dihalide with some multidentate Schiff bases was undertaken.

A recent publication² on diaryllead (IV) complexes of two tetradentate Schiff bases converges to our research programme and forces us to report a preliminary note on the work so far done in this laboratory on the Pb(IV) complexes with the following tetradentate and bidentate Schiff bases :

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by the following general method: 1m. mole, (2 m.moles for the bidentate ligands) of the Schiff base in dry methanol was allowed to react with 2 m.moles of NaOCH₃ in methanol, when the sodium salt of the respective ligand was obtained in solution. This was then added to 1 m. mole of diphenyllead dihalide suspended in 100 ml. of dry methanol. Dissolution of the lead-salt indicated the starting of the reaction. The mixture was refluxed for 1-2 hr. The complexes were precipitated from the clear reaction-mixture either during the reflux or on standing for sometime. These were

filtered, washed with a little solvent and dried in vacuum over fused CaCl₂. Sometimes 2-3 drops of water facilitated the precipitation of the complex.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are yellow, air-stable and are not easily attacked by water or alkali. The latter property indicates the hydrolytic stability of the complexes. They have low solubility in common organic solvents and are non-electrolytes.

The analytical data and conductance values (Table I) correspond to the general formula $\phi_2 \text{Pb(L)}$ and $\phi_2 \text{Pb(L')}_2$ where LH₂ is a tetradentate Schiff base (I-VI) and L'H, a bidentate Schiff base (VII-IX).

The broad band of the ligands in the region ~ 300 nm are replaced by more complicated bands, when they are coordinated with Pb(IV)-compound.

(LH₂ = A TETRADENTATE SCHIFF BASE)

(L'H = A BIDENTATE SCHIFF BASE)

NOTES

The bands in the region 220–280 nm which appear both in the case of the ligands and the complexes, are attributed as π - π^* benzenoid bands³.

TABLE I

Complexes	Decomposition temp. (°C)	% of Pb		% of N	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
1. ϕ_2 Pb(L _I)	235	33.01	32.92	4.47	4.37
2. ϕ_2 Pb(L _{II}) (orange yellow)	232	30.67	30.41	4.15	4.08
3. ϕ_2 Pb(L _{III})	—	„	30.05	„	4.25
4. ϕ_2 Pb(L _{IV})	205	„	31.09	„	4.22
5. ϕ_2 Pb(L _V) (melts)	177	31.71	32.05	4.29	4.20
6. ϕ_2 Pb(L _{VI})	224	27.57	27.29	3.73	3.69
7. ϕ_2 Pb.2(L _{VII})	234	27.50	27.57	3.72	3.85
8. ϕ_2 Pb.2(L _{VIII})	201	26.43	26.98	3.58	3.61
9. ϕ_2 Pb.2(L _{IX})	176	24.62	25.45	3.33	3.50

In the i.r. all the ligands show absorption bands in the region 2800–2600 cm^{-1} , due to the presence of intramolecular H-bonded OH groups and around 1280 cm^{-1} due to the phenolic C–O stretching frequency. No such bands are shown by the complexes. Furthermore, the C = N stretching frequency of the ligands in the region 1640 cm^{-1} are shifted by 15–20 cm^{-1} in the cases of the complexes. These show the participation of the azomethine groups and the phenolic (–OH) groups of the ligands in the complex formation.

Further work to establish the probable structure of these complexes and also on the reaction of these types of Schiff bases and other nitrogen-containing ligands with diphenyl-lead dihalides is in progress and the results will be communicated in due course.

References

1. S. N. PODDAR, C. JAMES and N. S. DAS, Proceedings of the Convention of Chemists, C.S.I.R. (India), 1971, p. 40.
2. BARBIERI, BIANCA and RIVAROLA, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1972, B387, 126.
3. K. CHATTERJEE and B. DOUGLAS, *Spectro. Chem. Acta.*, 1965, 21, 1625.

Studies on Some 4(7)-Iodobenzimidazoles

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IN view of very few iodobenzimidazoles reported so far¹, it was considered worthwhile to prepare a few 4(7)-iodobenzimidazoles. These were prepared from the corresponding diamines, reported by us

earlier. With formic and acetic acid, high yields of benzimidazoles were obtained (*vide exptl.*) but with a few other acids e.g., propionic, valeric, phenylacetic, chloroacetic and *p*-methoxyphenylthioglycolic acids evolution of vapours of iodine was observed indicating decomposition and pure iodobenzimidazoles could not be isolated. Condensation with amides also failed. Potassium ethyl xanthate, however, condensed smoothly to give the iodobenzimidazole in high yield.

The IR spectra of the compounds prepared agreed well with those of halobenzimidazoles².

Experimental

4(7)-Iodo- and 2-Methyl-4(7)-iodobenzimidazole :

The following adaptation of Phillip's method was used :

3-Iodo-*o*-phenylenediamine (0.02 mole), organic acid (0.1 mole) and 4(*N*)HCl (2.3 ml) were refluxed for 45 min, then diluted with water, cooled and neutralised with ammonia. The optd. solid was filtered, washed and recrystallised. 4(7)-Iodobenzimidazole (76%), violetish white needles (ethanol), m.p. 191°–92°. Lit.⁶ m.p. 188–189°.

$\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{IN}_2$ requires C—34.5, H—2.1%
Found C—34.6, H—1.9%.

2-Methyl-4(7)-iodobenzimidazole (64%), cream coloured needles (ethanol), m.p. 185°–187°.

$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{IN}_2$ requires C—37.2, H—2.7%
Found C—36.9, H—2.9%.

2-Mercapto-4(7)-iodobenzimidazole :

The Procedure given in Organic Synthesis⁹ was followed. Yield 80%, light yellow shining needles, m.p. 277°–78°(d).

$\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{IN}_2\text{S}$ requires C—30.4, H—1.8%
Found C—30.8, H—2.1%.

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References

1. J. R. R. HOOVER and A. R. DAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 4324, 5652.
2. R. M. ACHESON, G. A. TAYLOR and M. L. TOMLINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3750.
3. D. B. M. SCOTT, M. L. ROYER and C. ROSE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 2165.
4. H. M. KISSMAN, R. G. CHILD and M. S. WEISS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1185; H. B. GILLESPIE, M. ENGLMAN, F. SPANO and S. CRAFF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 2245; W. R. STEGART and A. R. DAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 4391; D. JERCHELL, German Pat. 888,032, 27 Aug. 1953; *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, 52, 348; Merch & Co., Brit. Pat. 783,306, 18 Sept. 1957, *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 51, 10497.
5. J. J. LEAVITT, U.S. Pat. 2,773,896, 11 Dec. 1956; 2,793,192, 21 May 1957; *Chem. Abs.* 1957, 51, 4726, 13411; T. W. PFIRRMANN, German Pat. 811,122, 16 Aug. 1951. *Chem. Abs.*, 1954, 48, 9735.